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INNOVATIVE PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ENSURING FAMILY STRENGTH. INFLUENCE OF FAMILY ENVIRONMENT ON THE FORMATION OF TALENT IN SCHOOL STUDENTS.

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Annotation: *In this article, the family plays an important role of the external environment in the development of talent in schoolchildren. Family is a part of society, in which a new person is born, it is the elementary school of life for a small social group. Parents, as the child's first teacher and educator, must first be psychologically prepared, talent is a specific form of abilities that ensure successful performance.*

Keywords. *Family, talent, children, parents, ability, external environment, heredity, school, development, upbringing, professional training of teachers.*

With the various models of giftedness currently available, most psychologists believe that internal factors such as intelligence, creativity, motivational and personality characteristics, as well as factors of the social environment, are fundamental to the development of giftedness in children.

According to the well-known Uzbek psychologist B.R. Kadirov, the family plays an important role in the development of children's abilities and talents, and in this, the proper organization of the child's activities by parents, hereditary characteristics passed from generation to generation, and the psychological composition of the family as a whole environment is important. In this regard, the scientist writes: «Family can serve not only as a natural environment for a child, so that he can develop his potential, but also explains the formation of the most delicate aspects of communicative relations and the dependence of talent on heredity». Educational conditions, characteristics of family education, cultural environment, etc. They are the most important components of the social factor of development. Experimental studies of the influence of parents on the developmental characteristics of their children are mainly related to the study of self-esteem, children's success in one or another field, and their ideas about their abilities with the social expectations of parents. From the point of view of pedagogy, the environmental variability of intelligence indicators is mainly related to the variability of the environment within the family. In relation to it, the external, cultural

environment serves as a general basis for development. Thus, the "environment within the family" has the greatest influence of all social factors. O.M. Dyachenko proposed to take into account the development of talent as an additional factor that ensures the realization of abilities in specific activities of children. The talent development model is presented by him in the form of three blocks. Thus, the developing personality is affected by external and internal factors. The purpose of identifying talent is to study the factors that cause talent, to study the psychological and personal characteristics of gifted children, and to acquire guidelines and tools for working with gifted children. Information about gifted children and their psychological characteristics, ability, talent, talent concepts is important. Factors affecting the process of teaching and learning gifted children include:

- 1- Environmental factors; these factors are related to the child's place of residence and growth. It is believed that everything around them can affect their learning. Environmental factors allow children to develop skills according to their habits. For example, a child raised in the city with daily access to tablets, computers, video games, and cell phones can improve their technology skills because they see it every day. A child growing up in the field will have the opportunity to improve his skills in agriculture, animal husbandry and other fields. However, this is not an indicator that one child is smarter than another, but that everyone can improve their skills based on what they see and do on a regular basis.
2. Signs of talent. Signs of giftedness are characteristics that are manifested in the real activity of a gifted child and are evaluated as a result of observing his actions. The signs of talent are related to the level of activity implementation. Before discussing the characteristics of giftedness, it is necessary to discuss the concepts of "will" and "can". Before discussing the characteristics of giftedness, it is necessary to discuss the concepts of "will" and "can". Motivation characterizes the child's attitude to one or another aspect of his activity, as well as to his own activity. The instrumental aspect of a gifted child's character is observed in the following signs. The presence of special strategies of activity, the activity of a gifted child is distinguished by its uniqueness and efficiency, accordingly, 3 main levels of activity success related to its implementation strategy are distinguished: In the conditions of rapid mastering of activity and finding a solution to the situation given to its implementation, new-success and creation of activity, application of new-methods as a result of deep mastering of science are approached with a different perspective. There are different manifestations of talent according to the characteristics of the child's goal promotion, psychological opportunities for reality, and age. One of the factors preventing the manifestation of talent is the lack of necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities. If children acquire the necessary knowledge, their talent will begin to manifest. In some cases, difficulties in a child's development

mask his talent. For example, anxiety, fear, conflicts can weaken his ability. On the other hand, the manifestation of talent also depends on the family's well-being. It is clear to us that financially well-off children have wide opportunities in all aspects, therefore, the manifestation of talent is "short-handed" in some situations, while the children of low-income families who depend on them want to demonstrate their talent. The unique features of gifted children make our life colorful and useful for society. Firstly, the gifted people are sensitive to everything and have a strong sense of fairness; they will be able to change and innovate social relations. The second characteristic is the activity of knowledge and the high level of development of the intellect, which allows obtaining new information about the environment. Talent is a specific form of abilities that ensure successful performance. The mutual compatibility of abilities serves to fill the gaps in other abilities. General abilities ensure the possibility of a person, development of his activity; It reflects the character of the ability, the natural, unique aspects of the abilities, the basis of success in the activity; A gifted child is brilliant in one or another activity. Sometimes, one of the internal conditions is talent, a child distinguished by continuous success. Today, many psychologists recognize that the development of talent is the result of a complex interaction between heredity (hereditary ability) and social environment (play, study, work processes). But one cannot deny the role of psychological mechanisms of self-education of a person, which lies at the basis of the formation of this individual talent. Many psychologists consider creativity (creative potential) to be an important and independent factor of talent. There are different manifestations of talent according to the psychological capabilities of the child and the characteristics of the age period. One of the factors preventing the manifestation of talent is the lack of necessary knowledge, skills, and qualifications. If children acquire the necessary knowledge, their talent will begin to manifest. It is necessary to identify the talent of students in the period of primary school and develop it. It is necessary to create all conditions for learning. The development of a person is first of all interrelated with the family in which he is born and grows up and his environment. If in the family, the parents recognize the child's personality and uniqueness, based on the child's age characteristics, capabilities and interests, then the child will become more and more demanding and aspirational. Especially at the age of development in kindergarten and adolescence, it is important for adults to give certain initiatives to the child, treat his opinion with respect, often ask "What do you think?" His appeal to his opinion allows free thinking and expressing an independent point of view.

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